

A Spatial Data Infrastructure Using Modern Standards: Lessons Learned from the eMOTIONAL Cities Project

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ABSTRACT

The environment we live in affects our mental health and well-being. The eMOTIONAL Cities project has set out to understand how the natural and built environment can shape the feelings and emotions of those who experience it. Employing a cross-disciplinary, data-driven approach, the project generated numerous datasets from traditional GIS-based fields like urban planning and from other disciplines such as neuroscience. The common denominator between all these datasets is the geospatial dimension. A primary goal was to assemble these disparate datasets into a Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI), enabling scientists and eventually the general public to discover and access the data for analysis and decision-making purposes.

Standards are crucial for ensuring interoperability, data consistency, and efficiency across diverse applications and platforms and thus they are at the core of every SDI. OGC API is a family of modern Standards from the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC), which leverages modern web technologies such as OpenAPI, REST and JSON. Although very appealing to web developers, they are relatively new compared to the first generation of OGC Web Services (e.g.: WFS, WMS). The eMOTIONAL Cities SDI demonstrates that it is now possible to share geospatial data using OGC API with a stack of Free and Open Source Software. In this article we share our journey during the process of implementing the SDI, and how we navigated the technological and human challenges of adopting emerging technologies in constant development.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 2016, the paper 'The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship' (Wilkinson et al., 2016) marked a significant milestone in scientific data management. It established a set of principles, aimed at making research data Findable, Accessible and ultimately Reusable (FAIR). They placed particular emphasis on the fact that it applies to both human-driven and machine-driven activities, a specific focus that distinguishes them from many similar initiatives.

The importance of the FAIR principles is increasingly recognised within large-scale research initiatives, such as the H2020 European projects. Funded by the European Union, these projects emphasize the need for rigorous data management practices aligned with FAIR principles, ensuring that data generated across diverse disciplines is preserved, shared, and reused to maximize impact (European Commission, 2016).

This emphasis on FAIR data management is particularly relevant to GIS data, which often underpins critical decision-making processes in urban planning, environmental management, and public health (Liu et al., 2022). There is a growing recognition of GIS data potential to improve data

production, storage, exchange, and processing and to support and enhance recent technological developments such as artificial intelligence, crowdsourcing, data spaces, digital twins and cloud computing.

The eMOTIONAL Cities project (eMOTIONAL Cities consortium, 2022) aimed to investigate the complex interplay between the natural and built environment and human emotions. To support this research, we developed a Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) that integrates disparate datasets from neuroscience, urban planning, and environmental sciences. This SDI serves as a crucial tool for facilitating data sharing, collaboration, and analysis within the project consortium and beyond.

The design of the eMOTIONAL Cities SDI extends beyond traditional GIS applications. Our goal was to create a user-friendly platform accessible to researchers across various disciplines, including those unfamiliar with geospatial data. By adhering to FAIR principles, we aimed to ensure the data's findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability, promoting its value for both human and machine-driven analysis.

The SDI's development was guided by the recognition that GIS data can play a vital role in understanding urban environments and their impact on human well-being. By integrating diverse datasets and providing a user-friendly interface, we sought to empower researchers to explore new insights and contribute to a deeper understanding of the complex relationship between the built environment and human emotions.

2. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

In geospatial data management, standards and software are crucial in ensuring the FAIRness of data. Open standards, such as those developed by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC), alongside Free Open Source Software (FOSS), are particularly important as they promote interoperability and democratise access to geospatial tools (Open Geospatial Consortium 2024).

OGC plays a critical role in supporting the FAIR principles through its comprehensive suite of standards for geospatial data (Jiménez, R. C. et al. 2017). OGC standards address three key components essential to a FAIR framework: data, metadata, and infrastructure. These standards include data format and transfer protocols which facilitate data accessibility and reusability across platforms. Equally important are semantic interoperability standards, which ensure a shared understanding of data, making it usable across diverse systems and contexts.

Traditionally, SDIs have relied on OGC's W* service interfaces (e.g., WMS, WFS, WCS), which often use XML-based protocols. However, recent advancements have introduced new architectural approaches that are more web-native, emphasizing machine-actionability and data-centricity (Simoes, J., & Cerciello, A. 2021). Modern web-based APIs offer several advantages, including simplified data processing, support for multiple encodings (e.g., JSON, HTML, JSON-LD, YAML), and seamless integration into various tools. These APIs, often designed with a RESTful architecture, enable easier data discovery through search engines like Google and Bing (Kotsev et al., 2020) while minimizing bandwidth usage. The OpenAPI specification (OpenAPI Initiative, 2011) further enhances these APIs by providing vendor-independent documentation and interactive testing capabilities.

OGC has embraced this shift with its new family of standards, known as OGC APIs (Open Geospatial Consortium. 2023a). OGC APIs are designed to simplify the provision and use of geospatial data on the web, enabling seamless integration with various other types of information. Building on the foundation of earlier OGC Web Service Standards (such as WMS, WFS, WCS, and WPS), these APIs adopt a resource-centric approach that leverages modern web development practices. Structured as modular "building blocks," OGC APIs allow for the creation of

customized APIs for web-based access to geospatial content (Open Geospatial Consortium. 2023b).

Furthermore, the W3C's Spatial Data on the Web Best Practices (SDW-BP) document (Spatial Data on the Web Best Practices, 2023) underscores the importance of data discovery and reusability in spatial data infrastructures. OGC APIs directly address these principles by enabling search engine indexing of geospatial data using standardized formats and APIs. For instance, OGC API - Features allows for the discovery and retrieval of vector data through a well-defined interface, while OGC API - Tiles facilitates the creation of interoperable tiled map services.

3. THE EMOTIONAL CITIES SDI

The eMOTIONAL Cities project established a Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) for managing and sharing the data it produced (Simoes and Cerciello, 2022a). Initially, we were cautious about adopting OGC APIs exclusively, due to concerns about the maturity of the standards and the availability of ready-to-use implementations. Back then, some OGC API components were still under development, and not many implementations were available yet. This led us to initially create an SDI that contained both a modern and legacy stack (Simoes and Cerciello, 2022b). However, in the past two years, there have been considerable developments in OGC API Standards, with many Standards having parts approved and implementations catching up on those developments. One implementation in particular, pygeoapi (pygeoapi development team, 2018), is exemplary in terms of the Standards development process, by participating actively in the OGC Code Sprints and by being an Early Implementer (EI), and even a Reference Implementation (RI), of several OGC API Standards. It embodies the new OGC paradigm, where the development of the Standard goes hand in hand with the development of implementations, resulting in published Standards which are market-ready.

After a process of gathering high-level requirements among the project partners, we have selected Standards to enable the publication of feature data (OGC API - Features), tiles of geospatial information (OGC API - Tiles), sensor data (SensorThings API) and metadata (OGC API - Records). Although that was not the case when we started this work, they are now all approved Standards.

The SDI uses a stack of FOSS software, with pygeoapi at its core and several supporting services. To ease the deployment and reproducibility of the system, the services were virtualized into docker containers and orchestrated using docker-compose (see Figure 1). This resulted in a system that is infrastructure agnostic and can be deployed in any Cloud Service Provider

(CSP) in a matter of minutes. The code is available on GitHub with an MIT license (Jo and Aontnio Cerciello, 2023).

Figure 1 - Architecture of the eMOTIONAL Cities SDI. OGC Standards server implementations are highlighted in blue, while storage backends are highlighted in pink.

We have also set up pipelines to enable both humans and machines to ingest data and metadata into the SDI (see Figure 2) and extensive documentation about how to access the SDI, using clients such as QGIS, MapStore or jupyter notebooks (Simoes and Cerciello, 2023).

Figure 2 - Pipeline for ingesting data and metadata into the eMOTIONAL Cities SDI.

The SDI is live at <http://emotional.byteroad.net/> and includes over one hundred collections from five different cities: Lisbon, London, Copenhagen, Tartu, and Lansing. It includes collections characterizing the physical environment (e.g., Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), annual mean NO₂ concentration), the built environment (e.g., buildings with repair needs ratio, average age of buildings), socio-economic aspects (e.g., Area Deprivation Index, number of people who travel by bicycle to work), health data (e.g., crude percentage of adults with depression, mortality rate, prevalence rates of mental health issues in London) (see Figure 3), and results of experiments (e.g., London outdoor walk test data: air quality temperature, sound pressure levels). The data can be discovered and queried in the OGC API - Records searchable catalogue: <https://emotional.byteroad.net/catalogue>

Figure 3 - “Prevalence rates of mental health issues in London” dataset, accessed on QGIS using OGC API - Features.

The SDI has had a couple of iterations before reaching its current format (Cerciello and Simoes, 2024). First and foremost, not all the OGC API parts we selected were published and implemented, which led us to introduce another component, publishing the same data using the first generation of OGC Standards (e.g.: WFS, WMS, WMTS) (Cerciello and Simoes, 2022). To a certain extent, that component could be removed now, although certain products may not have implemented OGC APIs yet and some users may be more familiar with the previous generation of OGC Standards. In the second release (Cerciello and Simoes, 2023) we added an implementation of SensorThings API (FROST), which addressed some needs of neuroscientists, in terms of storing and publishing information about sensors and measurements (See Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Details of a STA collection, being accessed in QGIS.

SensorThings API data is proxied through pygeoapi and transformed into a feature collection that GIS scientists can consume without the need for specific STA tools. Figure 5 summarizes the different stakeholders of the SDI, whose needs we tried to address using a variety of OGC Standards.

Figure 5 - Main stakeholders of the eMOTIONAL Cites SDI, mapped to OGC Standards.

One of the improvements of this SDI was the reuse of a single backend technology, Elasticsearch, to support OGC API - Features, OGC API - Tiles and OGC API - Records. Elasticsearch (Elastic, 2024) is a distributed, RESTful search and analytics engine, scalable data store, and vector database with geospatial capabilities. The “mvt-elastic” pygeoapi plugin leverages the Elasticsearch capability of generating vector tiles on the fly (Vera and Neiryck, 2022) to publish vector data as OGC API - Tiles (see Figure 6). This plugin was added during the course of this project (Simoes, 2023), enabling the eMOTIONAL Cities SDI to publish both OGC API - Features and OGC API - Tiles from a single Elasticsearch index.

Figure 6 - Vector tiles are very suitable for creating web maps, as they combine fast data delivery along with design flexibility.

This screenshot shows a LeafLet-based application that consumes one of the eMOTIONAL Cities collections.

It should also be mentioned that Elasticsearch was the only component of the SDI stack that did not have an Open Source license. As of August 2024, Elastic has added an AGPL license, which is an Open Source Initiative (OSI) approved license (Banon, 2024).

Considering the SDI was going to be used by scientists for the purpose of analysis, we also wanted to experiment with an emerging Standard in the field of cloud-native geospatial. GeoParquet (Geoparquet.org, 2024) is an open-source

column-oriented data storage format, which provides efficient data compression and encoding schemes with enhanced performance to handle complex data in bulk. Although GeoParquet started as a community effort, it is now on the path to become a full-fledged OGC Standard (Openeospatial, 2024) and it already features a vibrant ecosystem of implementations. We have converted more than one hundred eMOTIONAL Cities datasets to geoparquet using a semi-manual pipeline, which is documented in a blog post (doublebyte, 2024). The GeoParquet files are advertised through a link on the metadata records, which uses an item type “application/vnd.apache.parquet”. It is worth noting that GeoParquet files are considerably smaller than GeoJSON (our default format for OGC API) and even than binary formats such as GeoPackage or GeoJSON (See Figure 7).

Figure 7 - Size comparison between different formats to download eMOTIONAL Cities datasets, on an average-size dataset

Replacing the existing formats by GeoParquet would result not only in storage savings (and consequently cost savings), but also in bandwidth savings. This is particularly relevant for the use cases where analysis combines multiple datasets.

From the technological point of view, the major challenge in building this SDI was to adopt (at the time) candidate Standards, that were still evolving and, in some cases, not fully implemented or completely up to date in the implementation. However, the fact that we selected a Free and Open-Source tool, enabled us to make contributions to the project. The fact that pygeoapi was participating actively in the OGC Code Sprints, ensured that it kept aligning with the changes in the specification and even contributed towards improving it, by providing feedback to the Standards Working Groups. By joining the FOSS project and joining the OGC Code Sprints, we were able to minimize the technological challenges mentioned earlier.

From a human perspective, one of the main challenges was encouraging project partners to proactively share their data through the SDI. While some partners were autonomous,

efficient, and quickly understood the documentation and instructions provided—contributing their data accordingly—the overall process of data contribution was often complex and time-consuming. Moreover, obtaining high-quality metadata proved even more difficult than acquiring the data itself.

Partners with a solid background in data science or software development were notably more successful in navigating this process, indirectly highlighting the potential complexity of the solution for others. Despite the primary goal of the implemented pipelines being to simplify lower-level, GIS-specific tasks, these workflows may have still been too challenging.

To tackle this challenge, we put a lot of effort into outreach and education, creating detailed step-by-step guides on GitHub, and running webinars and workshops.

Having structured the development process with Agile methodology, it has also been possible to improve the proposed solutions in several aspects, listening to partners' feedback. We believe that at least some of these efforts were successful.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The experimental nature of this project has allowed us to explore novel approaches to Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) design and implementation. Our experience demonstrates the promising potential of OGC APIs in providing a flexible and scalable foundation for modern SDIs.

The adoption of OGC APIs has proven to be versatile, and capable of addressing a wide range of typical use cases within the GIS domain. Moreover, these standards have shown their adaptability to emerging fields, such as neuroscience. The successful integration of SensorThings API highlights the OGC API's potential to meet the specific needs of diverse domains.

The ongoing development efforts by the OGC and its working groups have significantly contributed to the maturity and robustness of OGC API specifications. This rapid progress is indicative of the growing interest and commitment to these standards within the geospatial community.

Fundamental to the success of the project was the use of FOSS solutions, which represented an opportunity to build a large part of the infrastructure on solid foundations, focusing only on the most emerging aspects of the project. At the same time, the fact that the SDI and all the developments on the individual derived tools are on open software means that the work carried out can be a starting point for further future projects.

By sharing our experiences and lessons learned, we hope to inspire others to adopt OGC APIs in their SDI projects. We believe that widespread adoption will foster further development and innovation within the open-source community, leading to more complete and high-quality software solutions.

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